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Abstract:

SSHOC Deliverable 5.3 outlines the SHARE accelerometer study and demonstrates how the data access plan conforms to the FAIR principles.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is a result of Task 5.1 of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, focusing on the legal, ethical, and technological issues of access to biomedical data. The task deals with the challenge of adapting the FAIR principles to the access of biomedical data available for the research community. As an intermediate step to the actual data access, this deliverable provides the data access plan for making accelerometer data available. This report describes the data access plan for accelerometer data collected within the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) and aims to inform and guide other researchers, survey methodologists and data archives.

Besides many other information, SHARE collects a wide variety of information on health of the population aged 50 and older. Objective health measures have been an important part of SHARE from its beginning. In its eight wave, SHARE implemented the collection of accelerometer data to objectively measure physical behaviour. SHARE Wave 8 fieldwork started in October 2019. The first accelerometers were sent out one month later. In March 2020, the entire fieldwork was stopped due to the COVID-19 pandemic and ensuing regulations that prevented the continuation of face-to-face interviews (see Scherpenzeel et al. forthcoming). Accelerometer data differ from traditional survey data, as they cannot be released immediately after collection and data cleaning, but they need to be processed and aggregated using specific statistical packages. The raw accelerometer data may not be accessible to external researchers, instead aggregated information will be published as generated variables alongside the regular SHARE data.

This report shortly sums up the implementation of the accelerometer data collection in SHARE and describes how the FAIR principles are implemented in the access and documentation of SHARE data: the data are made “findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable” for the scientific community. Regarding user access, the generated variables based on the accelerometer data do not differ from the traditional SHARE data. They are freely accessible, and the regular conditions of use apply.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
ID	identifier
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

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1. Introduction

The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) is an interdisciplinary panel study among the population aged 50 plus in 28 European countries and Israel. The aim of SHARE is to investigate questions that arise with individual as well as population aging. It covers a wide variety of topics including economic, social, and health related aspects of life. In addition to the questionnaire, physical performance tests such as grip strength, peak expiratory flow, walking speed, and chair stand are part of the SHARE interview. In 2019 and 2020, SHARE collected accelerometer data on a subsample of respondents, as additional objective measure of physical activity. Ten European countries participated in the accelerometer study.

Self-reported measures of physical activity in the elderly may suffer from “differential item functioning”, i.e. the inter-personal and inter-cultural variation in interpreting and using the response categories for the same question (Teresi and Fleishman 2007). Including an objective measure of physical activity is especially relevant in the SHARE sample, as old age and limitations in mobility make it difficult to compare respondents’ self-reported physical activity, because the interpretation of “moderate” and “vigorous” activities might differ as a consequence of individual health conditions and living situations. Moreover, country specific patterns in reporting may be prevalent (Kapteyn et al. 2018). A more objective assessment of physical activity can help to understand complex relations between physical activity, socio-economic conditions, health, health behaviour, and cognition.

Therefore, SHARE conducted the accelerometer project to measure the level of activity and sedentary behaviour of the elderly with a sensor to gather data that are comparable across countries. An accelerometer is a sensor that records acceleration, i.e., the rate of change of velocity. Accelerometers are integrated in wearable devices such as smart watches and activity trackers as well as smartphones. The acceleration is recorded typically several times per second to catch even short periods of acceleration.

The SHARE accelerometer study was implemented during the eight wave of SHARE, in 2019. SHARE Wave 8 fieldwork started in October 2019, the first accelerometers were sent out one month later. To capture physical activity, a subsample of SHARE respondents were asked to wear an accelerometer on the thigh for eight consecutive days, day and night, if possible without breaks. In March 2020, the entire fieldwork was stopped due to the COVID-19 pandemic and ensuing regulations that prevented the continuation of face-to-face interviews (see Scherpenzeel et al. forthcoming).

This report aims to provide guidance to researchers, research infrastructures, and data archives who intend to make accelerometer data available to the scientific community for research purposes. When providing accelerometer measurements to researchers, the specific characteristics of this type of data have to be taken into account: raw accelerometer sensor data are captured in high frequencies – typically 30, 50, or 100 measurements per second – that result in a high amount of data that cannot be easily interpreted. To provide researchers with meaningful and understandable information, additional data

processing steps are required before they can be analysed with the statistical techniques and models that are common in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). This report ascertains that SHARE accelerometer data, as all other regular SHARE survey data, comply with FAIR principles, as they are key for establishing open science as good scientific practice in the research community.

2. The SHARE accelerometer project

SHARE implemented the collection of accelerometer data in ten European countries during the main data collection of its eighth wave in 2019 and 2020. The study was conducted in ten countries to ensure geographic variation: Denmark, Sweden, Italy, Spain, Czech Republic, Poland, Slovenia, Belgium, France, and Germany. The gross sample was a stratified sample selected from each country's longitudinal sample before the fieldwork started. It included only the panel sample, i.e., respondents who participated in SHARE before to allow the use of information from previous interviews and excluded younger partners under 50 years. Strata were defined by age group and self-reported activity level in previous waves. There was no stratification by region or clustering within region. Detailed information about the sampling strategy, gross and net samples, and the study design will be available in Scherpenzeel et al. (forthcoming).

For all participating countries, ethical approvals were obtained from the respective national ethics committees. The approvals require specific information on the entire projects to be given to the participants in order to make their consent be informed. During the SHARE face-to-face interviews, the sampled respondents were asked for consent to participate in the accelerometer study and a short extra CAPI module was programmed to guide the interviewer through the consent gaining process. Interviewers stated explicitly that participation was voluntary and that results are only used for research purposes (not commercial). Respondents are further informed about data privacy measures and usage of data in an information letter that was provided together with the device. The SSHOC D5.1 provides "Guidelines for ethics considerations in making biomedical survey data FAIR" that should be taken into account when applying for ethics approval.

The coordination of the accelerometer study including the training of the interviewers was prepared centrally to keep all methods, processes, and used materials harmonized across countries (Scherpenzeel et al. forthcoming). Survey agencies received biweekly a list of respondents that should be interviewed by SHARE Central. The survey agencies then sent accelerometers to those respondents, and used the online platform DeviceCTRL, developed by Centerdata, to register which accelerometer was sent to which respondent at which date (see SSHOC M22 "Inventory of computing space needed for processing and analysing accelerometer data"). Either the interviewers or the survey agency contacted the respondents to check if they received the accelerometer kit, to give further explanations, and to offer assistance (by another home visit) if necessary or requested. Once accelerometers were received, respondents were asked to start wearing the device as described in the instructions kit and then return the device after

eight days of wearing time. Respondents were not supposed to change their usual activity pattern during the accelerometer measurement. As soon as the device was retrieved, the survey agency downloaded the respondent's activity data, refurbished the accelerometer, and uploaded the data as well as the information from the short questionnaire card (wear time, etc.) to the Device CTRL platform where it was downloaded by SHARE Central for further processing.

Valid accelerometer data have been collected from 855 respondents (exact numbers per country can be found in Scherpenzeel et al. forthcoming). Raw accelerometer data was processed at SHARE Central to provide users aggregated measures for activity on different levels in generated modules "gv_accelerometer_total", "gv_accelerometer_day", and "gv_accelerometer_hour". These modules differ in their structure compared to other modules, as measures derived from accelerometer data are provided on different levels (e.g., by day and hour) and therefore same respondents are included with several entries in these datasets. For future releases, it is planned to provide high frequency data – e.g., acceleration measurements on 5 second periods – to the SHARE users. In this case it will not be feasible anymore to provide information of all respondents in one single dataset. A different structure will be needed that provide one dataset per respondents.

Accelerometer data differ from traditional survey data for several reasons. First, there are no "answers" that can be stored digitally and made available together with the regular survey data. Instead, the "outcome" of the accelerometer collection is a large amount of high frequency sensor data. Second, due to the study design in SHARE, the raw sensor data are not the data that will be made available to the research community, but they require one further step: the processing with specific software. Only the hereby obtained metrics are the actual physical activity data that is published.

The data is processed with GGIR (Migueles et al. 2019), an open source package for the statistical computing software R (R Core Team, 2020). GGIR includes several steps of raw data processing to maximize the quality and comparability of generated measures. Raw accelerometer data is calibrated with respect to local gravity and deviations between devices (van Hees et al. 2014). Moreover, non-wear time is detected, and imputation of non-wear time is performed. Some measures based on GGIR are provided in the generated modules, e.g. the vector magnitude (cf. van Hees et al. 2013) and intensity gradient (Rowlands et al. 2018). For details on the data processing and generated variables, see SHARE Release Guide¹.

¹ SHARE Release Guide 1.0.0 of Wave 8 can be accessed via the SHARE homepage: <http://www.share-project.org/data-documentation.html>; accessed 15.07.2021

3. Data access plan confirming FAIR principles

The FAIR Guiding Principles for the publication of digital resources are a guideline for good scientific practice (Wilkinson et al. 2016, Wilkinson et al. 2018). These principles are met if research data is “findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable”. The utilisation of the FAIR Principles facilitates researchers to use existing data to its full potential.

SHARE has a general data access plan for all SHARE data including the accelerometer data that meet the FAIR Principles. As accelerometer data are released as a generated variable module as part of the SHARE data release, they do not require special qualifications to be used. User access regulations and measures taken to make all SHARE data (including the accelerometer data) FAIR are described in this chapter as well as on the SHARE homepage². Following sections 3.1 and 3.2 are based upon the SSHOC D5.2 “Data access protocol for DBSS data, linked to survey data, conforming FAIR principles (Access to biomedical data)” (Weiss 2020).

3.1 Access to accelerometer data

For accelerometer data the same rules and procedure concerning access apply as for all other SHARE data. SHARE data are available free of charge to all researchers world-wide via the internet. Data users must comply with the SHARE Conditions of Use³ including its ethics and confidentiality rules and the data protection and privacy requirements in accordance with Community and national data protection laws. The data may be used by registered SHARE users only.

To gain access to the SHARE data, all users are required to register individually with the SHARE Research Data Centre and to agree to the user conditions pertaining to the use of the SHARE data. Upon acceptance of the credentials, normally within a few working days, access will be given to the secure SHARE Research Data Centre website via a personal user ID and a password. The individual SHARE user is granted a simple, non-exclusive, non-transferrable right of use of the SHARE data. The data can then be downloaded by the individual user after successful registration. For a detailed description of user access regulations see SSHOC D5.2 “Data access protocol for DBSS data, linked to survey data, conforming FAIR principles (Access to biomedical data)” (Weiss 2020) or the SHARE web page⁴.

² SHARE Data Access: <http://www.share-project.org/data-access.html>; accessed 15.07.2021

³ SHARE Conditions of Use: <http://www.share-project.org/data-access/share-conditions-of-use.html>; accessed 17.11.2020

⁴ All details are available at User Registration: <http://www.share-project.org/data-access/user-registration.html>; accessed 15.07.2020

3.2 Compliance to FAIR principles

3.2.1 Findability

Data is supposed to be findable for both persons and software. Data and associated metadata should be assigned an abiding, unique identifier and registered in a comprehensible resource (Wilkinson et al. 2016), such as a data archive or institutional repository (Boeckhout, Zielhuis, and Bredenoord 2018).

To make datasets permanently identifiable and locatable SHARE uses DOI's. SHARE data is registered in the repository of da|ra, which links every DOI to a set of metadata, a collection of bibliographical and content information, referring to the registered dataset (title, author, publication date, copyright etc.). A DDI based SHARE Data & Documentation Tool is provided to users as a fast and easy-to-use web interface for browsing and searching the SHARE (meta)data.

3.2.2 Accessibility

SHARE data is accessible to the scientific community after individual registration under the conditions of use described in 3.1. The data is subject to national as well as European Union data protection laws. Users can retrieve the extensive documentation of the SHARE data on the website. Additionally, users can get more information and receive help by the SHARE user support points that answer questions and respond to user requests. Datasets are provided in the file types for Stata and SPSS, two commonly used software. However, users can access the data by means of other statistical software (e.g., R, SAS, or Python) as well because they support the import of different data types. The data is deposited at a public data archive by CentERdata, located at Tilburg University in Tilburg, Netherlands.

Overall, accelerometer data differ from traditional survey data in terms of project implementation (as specific devices are needed and the measurement period lasts for several days), they require additional privacy measures (e.g., oral, or written consent, information letter), and extensive processing is necessary prior to publication (statistical aggregation, calibration, and validation). The original raw sensor data may not be made accessible to data users at all. However, the final variables containing metrics derived from accelerometer measurements do not differ from the regular survey data. Therefore, the same conditions of use apply to their access as well. The easy access ensures *accessibility* in the sense of the FAIR principles.

3.2.3 Interoperability

SHARE data is available to researchers in Stata and SPSS format, two of the most common statistical software packages. However, users are not required to purchase a specific software to analyse the SHARE data. Provided datasets can be used with open software as well, e.g., R and Python. Independent of the statistical software, SHARE data can be combined with other data sources.

Interdisciplinary interoperability is achieved by using common standards and vocabularies. The SHARE (meta)data is comprehensively documented, based on DDI standards, to enable researchers from all disciplines to use it for their research and combine it with other datasets.

Because the accelerometer data differ such from the other survey data, extensive documentation will be provided to the user including a description of how the ready-to-use variables have been generated. Using open-source software for processing the raw accelerometer data and generating easy-to-use variables make the provided data user-friendly and comparable to other accelerometer studies. Metadata for accelerometer data in SHARE is documented along the regular SHARE data and available in a similar manner in the SHARE Data and Documentation Tool⁵, which strictly follows DDI standards. The documentation will also describe possible metadata such as fieldwork conditions that will be included into the published dataset. This documentation will further increase the interoperability of the data.

3.2.4 Reusability

SHARE accelerometer data, as the SHARE data in general, is not restricted in re-use, except for commercial use. Reusability is assured by archiving the data accompanied by a detailed documentation of the data and meta data.

Data re-use of SHARE data is also increased by providing additional datasets that help users in handling the data. Accelerometer measurements are provided in a generated module that contain commonly used metrics. Other information are also available as generated modules (e.g., imputations, aggregation of health data, ISCED-codes). For student training and researchers who have little experience in quantitative analyses of complex survey data, SHARE provides a teaching dataset.

Transparency of data re-use is being fostered by the request to all users of SHARE data to provide references to all forms of publications based on SHARE data to the central SHARE Coordination Team. The list of publications using SHARE data is available on the SHARE webpage.

⁵ www.share-project.org/data-documentation/data-documentation-tool.html; accessed 15.07.2021

4. Conclusion

Accelerometers are a valuable source for collecting physical activity data in the setting of a large survey such as SHARE. However, the data derived from such measurements differ from traditional survey data. The raw data may not be accessible to external researchers, but they have to be aggregated using statistical packages. The raw measured values are made comparable to values measured in other studies thanks to the open-source software mentioned above (GGIR), which includes several steps of raw data processing to maximize the quality and comparability of generated measures. This is part of SHARE's approach to make the data *interoperable* and *re-usable*.

Although accelerometer data differ from survey data conducted by a questionnaire in many ways, they do not differ in terms of user access. As part of the SHARE data release, they are accessible via the same procedure, stored at the same location, and therefore *findable* and *accessible* in the same way as all SHARE data. The same conditions as the regular SHARE data apply for the accelerometer data, too. This easy access to the accelerometer data is hoped to increase *re-use* of the data further.

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